

DISTANT DIMENSIONAL VOID: AN APERTURE IN 11 DIMENSIONS OF SPACETIME

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ABSTRACT

This paper will mostly focus on the 'Braneworld Scenario' of the 11 Dimensions of Space-time as predicted by "M-Theory"^[1] and will try to interpret the dimensions in a new philosophical approach, which may help the new possibilities of inter-dimensional travel thereby help us to solve many mysteries of the universe. This totally abstract idea will pave the way in which higher dimensions have a containment lower dimension and if anything can get to the "DISTANT DIMENSIONAL VOID" then all the 11 Dimensions of space-time will appear before him in a linear fashion and he has the degree of freedom to choose the best possible dimensions suitable for his travel. However, in the course of this paper, we will introduce 'what actually means by a dimensional void and how to get there hypothetically using philosophical approach and superstring theory. A complete mapping of 11 Dimensions has been presented in this paper. After that we will mathematically try to derive the volume of the universe that contained the 11-Dimensions.

METHODOLOGY AND INTERPRETATION

From Superstring Theory, we have come to know that there exist two types of strings, *The Open Strings* and *The Closed Strings*. The 'open strings' are 1-dimensional line which has endpoints on a 'P-Brane' where "P" stands for any number of dimensions less than or equal to 11. All these 'P-Branes' are floating in a 'Bulk'. And there exists the 2-dimensional closed strings as circles which have no endpoints on the 'P-Branes'. For example, a Photon is a 1-dimensional string that gets attached to the 'branes' because of their endpoints, whereas the Graviton is a closed string which has no endpoints and hence is not confined in between any two 'branes' and thereby can travel from branes to branes... or in other words a Graviton as a closed string can make interdimensional travel.

Now, as we know that, inside 2-dimensions, there is a confined 1-dimensions, inside 3-dimensions, there is a confined 2 dimensions, inside 4-dimensions, there is a confined 3-dimensions and henceforth in 11-dimensions, there is a confined 10 dimensions. Therefore, it is quite easy to conclude that, higher 'N' Dimensions contain all the lower 'N-1' Dimensions.

Consider a 6-dimensional 'Bulk'.... Here in the above picture you can see that, the 'bulk' contains all the intersecting '6-1'=5 Dimensional intersecting Branes and its very messy compared to the lower dimensions which contains less number of Branes like our 4-dimensional space-time which consists of 3-dimensional 'branes'.

However there is a different angle of looking at this scenario which is the main objective of this paper...

Here in this picture you can see a circle which represents the 'observable universe'... In this circle there are many concentric circles of different colors depicting the range of dimensions from 'D=1' to 'D=11', and as we have mentioned previously that a 11-dimension has all the '11-1=10' dimensional constants inside it. But what if there exists a 'Void' in these dimensions such that this "Void" is very small in 1-dimensions but very large in 11-dimensions, or in other ways the more the dimensions increases the more the area of the 'Void' increases. In 1-dimension the void is small, whereas in our 4-dimensional space-time, the void is quite bigger than 1-dimensions but in 11-Dimensions, the void is extremely prominent. This can be represented by the equation....

$$\text{NUMBER OF DIMENSIONS} \propto \text{AREA OF THE VOID}$$

If one can escape inside this dimensional void then a 'Linear Spatial Diversion' will be created like this....

So, if a person enters into the void then as a person he is 3-dimensional but everything else around him is dimension less. There is no dimensions whatsoever in this void or the 'Black Conic Region' in the above picture. Each dimension will appear in front of him in a linear fashion and he is free to choose which dimension, he wants to get into. Obviously, the void in 4-dimension is small than the void in 11-dimensions and therefore, its easy for 11-Dimensional being to get inside the void and then choose any appropriate dimensions he needs himself to enter. The fact is that, an 11-dimensional creature will not appear properly in his 'shape and form' in 4 dimensions. But rather his 'cross sections' will arrive in the lower dimensions and what we will see is a 'blob'. This 'DISTANT DIMENSIONAL VOID' is very much suitable for interdimensional travel and maybe if we can escape from the boundary or the domain of our enclosed dimensions, we can enter inside this void. Now, the fact is that, there lies an invisible boundary membrane separating the void and the dimensions and if this boundary membranes can be crossed then we can directly enter into the 'DISTANT DIMENSIONAL VOID' which is 'an aperture in the space-time'.

Once these membranes have been crossed, one can enter directly inside the void. As there are no dimensions, hence we can consider that while entering upon the void.... All these 1 – 2 – 4 – 5 – 6 – 7 – 8 – 9 – 10 – 11 'Dimensions' will appear as a linier fashion and as the divergence between the dimensions becomes prominent to the observer inside the void, he can enter in any dimensions as he like. But, in our 4-dimensional world, the void being comparatively small, the void is difficult to enter into. ***The Hypothesis is that 'if a person starts his journey from one side of a universe, then he will not come to the starting point as because there lies the membrane or the 'Void' which protects a '2πr' rotation then he will not reach the initial point as this gives a conjecture that our universe is not simply connected manifold'.***

If we consider the universe or the observable universe as a sphere then we can derive the following calculations based on the image below...

If we assume our universe a sphere, then the volume of the 'Dimensions' of the universe is the 'volume with the dimensions of the sphere' – 'volume of the cone' – 'volume of the hemisphere marked as green in the above picture' That is....

$$\frac{4}{3}\pi R^3 - \left(\frac{1}{3}\pi r^2 h + \frac{2}{3}\pi r^3\right)$$

Here R is the radius of the sphere, r is the radius of the cone and hemisphere and h is the height of the cone. Here the radius of the cone that is 'dimensional void' and the hemisphere 'marked green' are the same.

From another aspect if we take the Set **S** to be the set of 11 dimensions then we will also get ϕ as the empty set a subset and components of S as.... Every empty set is a subset of a set.

$$\mathbf{S} = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, \phi\}$$

Here ϕ is the dimensional void or the empty set.

REFERENCE

^[1] Duff 1998

Cremmer, Julia, and Scherk 1978

Nahm 1978